

Preparation of 2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-dipropionyl-diphenyl Sulphide

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The investigation on *p*-methoxypropiofenone was taken up with a view to studying the effect of methylation of the hydroxyl group on the reactivity of the molecule. It was found that the molecule was deactivated considerably.

p-Methoxypropiofenone afforded sulphide (I) when it was allowed to react with thionyl chloride in presence of finely divided copper. On nitration with HNO_3 (conc.), sulphide (I) provided 3-nitro-4-methoxypropiofenone, proving that the two aromatic nuclei were joined through the sulphur atom in position *ortho* to -OMe and *meta* to -COMe groups.

2,2'-Dimethoxy-5,5'-dipropionyl-diphenyl Sulphide (I).—Thionyl chloride (5 ml) was added to an intimate mixture of *p*-methoxypropiofenone (1 g.) and copper powder (1 g.). The reaction mixture was heated on a boiling water bath for about 15 minutes and then allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The red pasty mass, obtained after removal of excess of thionyl chloride and copper powder, was washed first with toluene and then with CS_2 , when a brown powder was obtained. It was crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 175°. (Found: S, 8.96. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{S}$ requires S, 8.94%).

It is highly soluble in acetone and acetic acid, sparingly soluble in ethanol, and insoluble in benzene, toluene, CS_2 , ether, and chloroform.

The same sulphide was obtained when *p*-methoxypropiofenone was allowed to react with sulphur dichloride.

2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones of (I) melted at 220-22°. (Found: S, 5.11. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires S, 4.85%).

3-Nitro-4-methoxypropiofenone.—Sulphide (I) (1g.) was added to a mixture of H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 ml) and HNO_3 (conc., 5ml) and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Next day it was diluted with water when a yellowish white solid separated, which was crystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 99-100°. It showed no lowering in melting point when mixed with a genuine specimen¹.